

Merger and Acquisitions (M&A) Goodwill Accounting: Principles and Practice

Alim Al Ayub Ahmed
and
Taposh Kumar Neogy

Abstract

The accounting for business combinations has been a fertile source of controversies, to which the accounting for goodwill generated from Merger & Acquisitions (M&A) has made major contributions. Practitioners continue to suffer amidst industry lobbying versus regulators quarrels, and therefore one can argue that in M&A goodwill accounting: "Those are my principles, and if you do not like them ... well, I have others", as Groucho Marx would say.

The replacement of amortisation of purchased goodwill and other intangible assets with definite life by impairment tests continues to raise concerns and therefore remains an accounting issue. Several authors, such as Hayn & Hughes (2006), questioned the superiority of impairment tests over amortisations, while Massoud & Raiborn (2003) suggested that managerial discretion in applying the goodwill impairment tests reduces the quality of reported earnings. Massoud & Raiborn (2003) also argued that SFAS No. 142 creates opportunities for earnings management, particularly in weak economic periods, where companies can undertake a "big bath", i.e., to recognise big impairment losses in a period when earnings are already negatively affected.

The early 2000's was characterised by an economic downturn, which has resulted in a recession in the USA in the period between March and November 2001, as defined by the National Bureau of Economic Research (NBER). The dot.com bubble collapse, the September 11 attacks, and the numerous accounting and corporate scandals that resulted in the Sarbanes-Oxley act, are some of the events that could equally trigger the recognition of massive losses following impairment testing in fiscal years 2001 and 2002. Significant impairment losses under SFAS 142 could only occur from

fiscal year 2002 onwards, as this standard was first adopted in fiscal year 2002 by most companies. Unsurprisingly, a big bath earnings management has occurred in 2002, as documented in the accounting and financial literature. There is however another fact that may have eased the happening of this "big bath": the change in the accounting regulation itself, which has diluted the negative impact on corporate earnings due to impairment charges.

A big bath earnings management has occurred in 2002, as documented in the accounting and financial literature (see e.g. Jordan & Clark, 2004, 2005). There is however another fact that may have eased the happening of this "big bath": the change in the accounting regulation itself, which has diluted the negative impact on corporate earnings due to impairment charges. By the means of financial reporting disclosures analysis, this paper examines several aspects of SFAS 142 adoption, namely its significant impact on corporate earnings reported in the USA.

1. Introduction

Before FASB's changes in accounting for business combinations in 2001, the managerial accounting choice preference was clear in the mergers & acquisitions field (M&A): pooling of interests method, regardless its use being conditional to its qualification for a uniting of interests (see e.g. Aboody et al., 2000; Anderson & Louderback III, 1975; Ayers et al., 2000, 2002; Copeland & Wojdak, 1969; Gagnon, 1967; Lys & Vincent, 1995; Nathan, 1988). Management wants to maximize results, and purchase was not a suitable method, as it required goodwill recognition and amortisation, with negative consequences on earnings. Indeed, early studies found that managerial discretion was used in business combinations accounting in order meet financial reporting

Alim Al Ayub Ahmed, Lecturer of Accounting, School of Business Administration, Asian University of Bangladesh, Bangladesh and Taposh Kumar Neogy, Lecturer, Department of Business Administration, Southern University, Bangladesh

objectives, namely to maximize reported earnings (Copeland & Wojdak, 1969).

As referred before, this appetite for pooling of interests was excessive. In fact, diverse anecdotal and empirical evidence suggested that companies could reshape M&A deals, incurring in extraordinary expenses, and even paying higher acquisition premiums, simply to meet AICPA's APB Opinion 16 pooling of interests criteria (see e.g. Aboody et al., 2000; Ayers et al., 2002; Davis, 1990; Hopkins et al., 2000; Linsmeier et al., 1998; Lys & Vincent, 1995; Robinson & Shane, 1990; Walter, 1999; Weber, 2004).¹

Despite the apparent advantages of pooling over purchase method, several studies detected that pooling method resulted in mechanical effects on companies' financial statements and on the analysis of the financial statements (Jennings et al., 1996; Vincent, 1997), while others documented that the short-window announcement returns were lower for companies pooling than for companies using purchase method (Davis, 1990; Hong et al., 1978; Martinez-Jerez, 2001).

According to Fields et al. (2001), whether shareholders benefit from managerial discretion and whether the benefits outweighed the costs is not clear. However, according to Louis (2004), literature suggested that pooling deals are "bad investment decisions" because managers miss the focus on cash-flows, as they are more concerned with reporting increasing earnings, and also because they constraint the management's ability to sell acquired assets after the acquisition (Lys & Vincent, 1995; Robinson & Shane, 1990). Unsurprisingly, Martinez-Jerez (2003) found that stronger negative market reaction to pooling M&A deals is linked to acquirers that have poor corporate governance.

On the one hand, pooling seemed to underperform purchase method, but on the other, its defenders raised their arguments loud when the FASB proposed to eliminate pooling. Apparently, as theorized by Watts & Zimmerman (1990, 1978). Among pooling supporters were certainly managers more concerned with their contracts, than with the effective economic consequences of the forthcoming changes in M&A accounting. Watts & Zimmerman (1978) suggested that accounting choice may affect shareholders' wealth in case managers' compensation contracts are coupled to financial

reporting performance. Indeed, while examining specific characteristics determining which business combinations accounting method is selected by the management, it was found that the percentage of insiders' ownership, and accounting-based compensation plans play a significant role (Dunne, 1990).

2. Literature *ex post* changes in M&A accounting

Following the effectiveness of the new business combinations accounting rules, the debate shifted from pooling elimination to the accounting treatment of purchased goodwill and other intangible assets. Amortisation versus impairment tests became the main issue. SFAS 142 replaced amortisation of acquired goodwill and other intangible assets with indefinite useful lives by impairment tests, keeping amortisation, under certain conditions, only for goodwill and intangible assets with finite useful lives. By doing so, the FASB added volatility to financial reporting. This fact was assumed in SFAS 142. When comparing the differences between SFAS 142 and APB Opinion 17, it is stated that (Financial Accounting Standards Board, 2001b: 5):

"Because goodwill and some intangible assets will no longer be amortized, the reported amounts of goodwill and intangible assets (as well as total assets) will not decrease at the same time and in the same manner as under previous standards. There may be more volatility in reported income than under previous standards because impairment losses are likely to occur irregularly and in varying amounts."

Certainly there will be more volatility, one could add. Regardless the merits of impairment treatment, which screens continuously for the value of purchased goodwill and other intangible assets, whether such volatility increases the quality of financial reporting, and the usefulness of its users, is not a clear matter. Perhaps the best judgement will come with time, but in the meantime some literature started to examine this issue, providing some early findings. In terms of examples of literature about impairments under SFAS 142, Hayn & Hughes (2006) questioned the superiority of impairment tests over amortisations, while Massoud & Raiborn (2003) suggested that the managerial discretion in applying the

¹ Conversely, Nathan (1988) did not find higher acquisition premiums for companies applying the pooling of interests method.

goodwill impairment tests reduces the quality of reported earnings. Massoud & Raiborn (2003) argue that SFAS No. 142 creates opportunities for earnings management, particularly in weak economic periods, where companies can undertake a "big bath", i.e., to recognize big impairment losses in a period when earnings are already negatively affected.

The early 2000's was characterised by an economic downturn, which has been declared as a recession in the USA by the National Bureau of Economic Research (NBER) in the period between March and November 2001. The dot.com bubble collapse, the September 11 attacks, and the numerous accounting and corporate scandals that resulted in the Sarbanes-Oxley act, are some of the events that could arguably trigger the recognition of massive losses following impairment testing in fiscal years 2001 and 2002. Significant impairment losses under SFAS 142 could only occur from fiscal year 2002 onwards, as this standard was adopted mostly for fiscal year 2002. Unsurprisingly, a big bath earnings management has occurred in 2002, as documented in the accounting and financial literature (see e.g. Jordan & Clark, 2004, 2005).

There is however another fact that may have eased the happening of this "big bath": the change in the accounting regulation itself, which has diluted the negative impact on corporate earnings due to impairment charges. This matter is to be studied in the following section.

Some literature cast doubts about the superiority of impairment tests over amortisations (vid. Hayn & Hughes, 2006), and other literature suggested that the managerial discretion in applying the goodwill impairment tests reduces the quality of reported earnings (e.g. Massoud and Raiborn, 2003).

3. Analysis of annual reports

This paper examines the effects of the effectiveness of the new business combinations accounting standards in financial reporting. Accordingly, this section examines whether the new business combinations accounting rules had any significant influence on the financial reporting of companies involved in M&A deals. This is arguably a relevant issue because changes in business combinations accounting have a

previous record of controversy as they often lead to significant changes in financial reporting.

3.1. Methodology of analysis

The methodology used in this paper is based on the examination of financial reports from large US corporations. Through the information available on their annual reports, particularly in statements on accounting changes, and in the financial statements notes, the effects on financial reporting due to the new business combinations accounting rules are examined. The financial reporting analysis also allowed estimating the impact of the new accounting standards on corporate results.

The analysis of the effects on financial reporting is not intended to formally test any hypothesis. The analysis has a simple proposition, which is to verify whether the changes in business combinations accounting resulted in significant impacts on the financial reporting. This statement could be regarded as a testable hypothesis. However, it is not the purpose of this paper, as this proposition will only be evaluated by the means of qualitative and quantitative analysis of financial reporting data. A part of the quantitative analysis will be cross-sectional.

3.2. Data sources

The sample for analysis, shown in the next section, is the result of the compilation of data collected from financial reports of companies that completed M&A deals in recent years, and that have reported business combinations accounting changes following the adoption of the new FASB's standards. The companies composing the S&P 500 index, effective after the close of 31 December 2004, were the centrepiece of the study, and therefore data has been collected from these companies' financial reports. S&P 500 index includes firms with large capitalization values, listed on both NYSE and NASDAQ. The fact these companies were listed enhanced the odds of involvement in M&A deals, as exchange markets ease the concretization of M&A deals.

In the USA, the Form 10-K is an annual filing which provides a comprehensive overview of the company for the period of a year. 10-K forms are often included in annual reports, although they are formally prepared to comply with the SEC, and the Securities Exchange Act requirements; while annual

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reports are primarily focused in investors. Since companies have to report material changes as a result of the adoption of new accounting standards, it is therefore possible to collect data directly from annual reports and 10-K forms.² The data was collected primarily from the 10-K forms. The SEC Filings and Forms (EDGAR), and the EDGAR Online Pro database, were the main data sources used.³ Data from annual reports was also examined in order to collect additional information about some companies. The data sources for annual reports were The Annual Reports Service, from Barron's, and several S&P 500 companies' websites.

3.3. Data collection

Since both SFAS 141 and SFAS 142 became effective during 2001, annual reports and 10-K forms have been examined since fiscal year 2001. Most companies have fiscal years ending in 31 December, or by the end of the year, and therefore the changes in business combinations accounting occurred in 2001 were likely to be disclosed immediately, i.e., from 2002's filings onwards. However, as discussed later in this section, filings up to year 2004 could still refer to 2001's changes in business combinations accounting.

3.3.1. New business combinations accounting standards disclosures

Both new business combinations accounting standards contain detailed provisions concerning disclosures on business combinations and on accounting changes, as shown in paragraphs 51 to 58 of SFAS 141 (Financial Accounting Standards Board, 2001a), and in paragraphs 44 to 47 of SFAS 142 (Financial Accounting Standards Board, 2001b). They are mostly to be presented in the notes to the financial statements. SFAS 142 also provides further guidance on disclosures in its Appendix C, by the means of illustrations. Much of the impacts reported by companies were based in such guidance.

An example of financial reporting disclosure on business combinations' new accounting follows for 3M Company. For

the year ended in 31 December 2001, 3M Company, registered as Minnesota Mining and Manufacturing Company, filed the Form 10-K405 in 11 March 2002, as required by the Securities Exchange Act of 1934. By standard, every reporting company devoted a section or specific paragraphs announcing the enforcement of the new business combinations pronouncements. In the first year of SFAS 141 adoption, 3M Company reported (Item 7, 2002):

"In June 2001, the Financial Accounting Standards Board issued SFAS No. 141, *Business Combinations*. SFAS No. 141 applies to all business combinations with a closing date after June 30, 2001. The most significant changes made by SFAS No. 141 are: 1) requiring that the purchase method of accounting be used for all business combinations initiated after June 30, 2001, and 2) establishing specific criteria for the recognition of intangible assets separately from goodwill."

This description resembles a commonplace, as it illustrates the way companies reported the generic changes in business combinations accounting. Overall, companies reported the existence of the new business combinations standard, SFAS 141, but no effects were to be disclosed, as pooling of interest was simply no longer an option. The adoption of SFAS 141 was therefore absolutely neutral from a financial point of view. When referring to both SFAS 141 and SFAS 142 it is stated that (Notes to Consolidated Financial Statements, 3M Company, 2002):

"These standards permit only prospective application of the new accounting; accordingly, adoption of these standards will not affect previously reported 3M financial information."

Since pooling of interests had been discontinued, no prospective application was therefore possible for SFAS 141. Companies simply informed whether they used pooling method before its elimination. However, a very different scenario was set for SFAS 142. Like for SFAS 141, companies produced a similar standard description for SFAS 142 (Item 7, 3M Company, 2002):

² In this paper, "annual report", "Form 10-K", and "annual filing" are interchangeably used.

³ In some cases the Form 10-K was not available and the Form 10-K405 was examined instead. Like the Form 10-K, the Form 10-K405 is also a SEC filing, but indicates a file violation resulting from the lack of disclosure of insider trading activities from the reporting company. The identification of the form as 10-K405, versus ordinary 10-K, was made by a company's officer or director, and not by SEC officials. Unsurprisingly, it resulted in inconsistent designations by companies. Accordingly, the SEC's Branch of Public Reference discontinued the requirement to designate a filing as a Form 10-K405, effective after 2002, and 10-K405 forms were no longer accepted by the SEC filings system.

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"The Financial Accounting Standards Board recently issued Statement No. 142, *Goodwill and Other Intangible Assets*, which will be adopted by the company effective January 1, 2002. Goodwill and intangible assets acquired after June 30, 2001, are subject immediately to the non-amortization and amortization provisions of this statement, while existing goodwill and other indefinite-lived assets will no longer be amortized beginning January 1, 2002. Goodwill will be subject to an impairment test at least annually".⁴

However, a more detailed examination on the accounting changes resulting from SFAS 142 adoption is provided in the notes, as shown in the two paragraphs quoted below (Notes to Consolidated Financial Statements, 3M Company, 2002):

"SFAS No. 142 primarily addresses the accounting for acquired goodwill and intangible assets (i.e., the post-acquisition accounting). The provisions of SFAS No. 142 will be effective for fiscal years beginning after December 15, 2001. The most significant changes made by SFAS No. 142 are: 1) goodwill and indefinite-lived intangible assets will no longer be amortized; 2) goodwill and indefinite-lived intangible assets will be tested for impairment at least annually (...); and 3) the amortization period of intangible assets with finite lives will no longer be limited to 40 years."

Indeed, further examination of 3M's Form 10-K405 reveals that the focus of business combinations accounting changes is on SFAS 142, as it is clearly assumed that:

"The principal effect of SFAS No. 142 will be the elimination of goodwill amortization. Amortization of goodwill and indefinite-lived intangible assets in 2001 was \$67 million (net income impact of \$51 million, or 12 cents per diluted share)".

The paragraph above identifies and illustrates the impact subject to analysis in this section. Since the effects from

SFAS 142's adoption are to be measured by the companies, no computation from the researcher is needed. This is an advantage for the researcher, as the risk of a biased data handling is avoided. Any possible computation flaws are therefore responsibility of the reporting companies.

Like its peers, 3M Company was amortising goodwill in wide periods, including the maximum amortisation ceiling. As referred to by 3M Company in its annual report notes, in the first quarter of 2001 three notable business combinations were completed using purchase method. The purchased intangible assets, including goodwill, were being amortised on a straight-line basis over the periods benefited, ranging from 4 to 40 years (Notes to Consolidated Financial Statements, 3M Company, 2002). As referred in the last quoted paragraph, if SFAS 142 would be adopted in 2001 the relief in losses as a consequence of the nonamortisation of purchased goodwill would be of \$51 million alone for 3M Company. This would result in a significant increase of earnings per share in 2001: from \$3.58 to \$3.70, a net impact of 12 cents. Although 12 cents in \$3.58 stand for *only* a 3.35% increase, evidence collected in this research, and to be shown later in this section, suggests the existence of significant higher impacts for most companies in the scope of the adoption of the new business combinations accounting standards.

The positive impact of the elimination of amortisation of acquired goodwill and other intangible assets on earnings was certainly minimized by the recognition of impairment losses, also under SFAS 142.⁵ At least for 126 and 40 companies in fiscal years 2002 and 2003, respectively, which have disclosed some type of impaired purchased goodwill and other intangible assets than goodwill, following SFAS 142

⁴ According to SFAS 142 (paragraph 43, 2001a), goodwill is the excess of cost of an acquired entity over the net amounts assigned to assets acquired and liabilities assumed in a business combination.

⁵ Under SFAS 141, business combinations companies are required to estimate the fair value of acquired intangible assets in the following manner: first, intangible assets must be categorized by type, such as customer lists, trademarks, patents, software, intellectual property, etc; second, intangible assets with an identifiable remaining useful life must be separated from those with an indefinite useful life. The latter is then classified as goodwill and must be subject to a two-step test for impairment under FASB 142, which companies were required to adopt by January 1, 2002. However, if goodwill and other intangible assets acquired in a transaction for which the acquisition date is after June 30, 2001, but before the date of fully adoption of SFAS 142, these assets are to be reviewed for impairment in accordance with APB Opinion 17, or with SFAS 121, as appropriate, until the date that SFAS 142 is applied in its entirety (Paragraph 51, Financial Accounting Standards Board, 2001b).

Under SFAS 142, the two steps of the goodwill impairment test are (Paragraphs 19-22, Financial Accounting Standards Board, 2001b): first, identifying potential impairments by comparing the fair value of a reporting unit to its carrying amount, including goodwill. Goodwill is not considered impaired as long as the fair value of the unit is greater than its carrying value. The second step is only required if an impairment to goodwill is identified in step one; second, comparing the implied fair market value of goodwill to its carrying amount. If the carrying amount of goodwill exceeds its implied fair market value, an impairment loss is recognized. That loss is equal to the carrying amount of goodwill that is in excess of its implied fair market value, and it must be presented as a separate line item on financial statements.

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adoption. In the universe of S&P 500 index companies, these impairing companies figures represent only around 25% and 8% in total, for 2002 and 2003, respectively.

Taking once again 3M Company as an example of accounting treatment, the impairment tests procedure under SFAS 142 was described in the following way (Note 1, 3M Company, 2003):

"Beginning January 1, 2002, goodwill will be tested for impairment annually, and will be tested for impairment between annual tests if an event occurs or circumstances change that would indicate the carrying amount may be impaired. Impairment testing for goodwill is done at a reporting unit level. Reporting units are one level below the business segment level, but can be combined when reporting units within the same segment have similar economic characteristics. 3M, at year-end 2002, had 20 reporting units under the criteria set forth by SFAS No. 142. The vast majority of goodwill relates to and is assigned directly to a specific reporting unit. An impairment loss would generally be recognized when the carrying amount of the reporting unit's net assets exceeds the estimated fair value of the reporting unit. The estimated fair value of a reporting unit is determined using earnings for the reporting unit multiplied by a price/earnings ratio for comparable industry groups, or by using a discounted cash flow analysis."

Although the accounting procedure for impairment testing seemed to be reasonably well described, and despite the multiple business combinations involving 3M Company in the preceding years, including 9 deals in 2002, no impairment charges were recorded for purchased goodwill in 2002 (Note 1, 3M Company, 2003):

"The company completed its assessment of any potential

impairment upon adoption of this standard and upon its annual assessment and determined that no impairments existed."

The absence of impairment charges was not an exclusive for purchased goodwill, as it was also extended for other intangible assets with indefinite life, such as patents, tradenames, and others, acquired from an independent party.⁶ In neither of the fiscal years examined, from 2001 to 2004, had 3M Company recorded any impairment loss related to SFAS 142's adoption.

For the present paper it would be more relevant to be aware of impairment charges in the first year of adoption of new business combinations accounting standards. As suggested before, overall, despite being considered a "big bath year", impairment losses recorded in 2002 were not as significant as one could expect. There are many possible justifications for this fact, but perhaps two simple reasons may explain reasonably why this happened. First, perhaps the most important reason for the absence of impairment charges was the lack of in-depth guidance regarding the application of impairment tests. It was also an upcoming intense period of accounting regulation changes.⁷ Second, conceivably some companies did not have much time to carefully proceed with impairment tests, in order to evaluate any possible impairment losses under SFAS 142. In the case of 3M Company, it was implicitly admitted that no extensive impairment tests were performed in a first stage of SFAS 142's adoption (Notes, 3M Company, 2002):

"A preliminary review indicated that no impairment existed at December 31, 2001".

However, this discussion is not considered to be relevant to the present research, and therefore only the impact on

⁶ Below is shown the treatment given by 3M Company to purchased intangible assets with an indefinite life (Note 1, 3M Company, 2003):

"Effective January 1, 2002, with the adoption of SFAS No. 142, intangible assets with an indefinite life, namely certain tradenames, are not amortized. Intangible assets with a definite life are amortized on a straight-line basis with estimated useful lives ranging from 2 to 17 years. Indefinite-lived intangible assets will be tested for impairment annually, and will be tested for impairment between annual tests if an event occurs or circumstances change that would indicate that the carrying amount may be impaired. Intangible assets with a definite life are tested for impairment whenever events or circumstances indicate that a carrying amount of an asset (asset group) may not be recoverable. An impairment loss would be recognized when the carrying amount of an asset exceeds the estimated undiscounted cash flows used in determining the fair value of the asset. The amount of the impairment loss to be recorded is calculated by the excess of the assets carrying value over its fair value. Fair value is generally determined using a discounted cash flow analysis. Costs related to internally developed intangible assets are expensed as incurred."

⁷ The accounting changes in early 2000's were not an exclusive from business combinations, as other FASB pronouncements became effective in the same period, such as: SFAS 140, Accounting for Transfers and Servicing of Financial Assets and Extinguishments of Liabilities a replacement of FASB Statement 125; SFAS 143, Accounting for Asset Retirement Obligations; SFAS 144, Accounting for the Impairment or Disposal of Long-Lived Assets, or SFAS 145, Rescission of FASB Statements No. 4, 44, and 64, Amendment of FASB Statement No. 13, and Technical Corrections. More accounting standards would be enforced in the upcoming years. Following several scandals that led to major corporate failures, the US Congress passed the Sarbanes-Oxley Act (SOX) of 2002, enacted in 30 July, in order to improve investors' protection from the possibility of fraudulent accounting activities by corporations.

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earnings from the non-amortisation of purchased goodwill and other intangible assets with indefinite life was examined in-depth.

3.3.2. Adoption and disclosure timing of SFAS 142 impacts

SFAS 142 is the most important of the new business combinations accounting standards for the present research, as the information to be collected from the annual reports is disclosed under its provisions. It is therefore critical to understand the process of disclosure and adoption of SFAS 142 by the companies. A brief chronology follows. After FASB issued the new business combinations accounting standards in June 2001, companies become likely to mention that fact immediately after in their annual reports. However, no impacts had to be disclosed immediately, as companies only needed to compulsorily adopt SFAS 142 provisions from fiscal year 2002 onwards.

Indeed, as SFAS 142 provisions were required to be applied starting with fiscal years beginning after 15 December 2001 (Paragraph 48, Financial Accounting Standards Board, 2001a), and as fiscal year ending in 31 December is the commonest financial reporting period, most S&P 500 companies adopted SFAS 142 immediately in 2002. However, companies with a fiscal year beginning after 31 December 2001 could defer adoption of SFAS 142 for 2003's fiscal year.⁸

Another justification for the immediate adoption of SFAS 142 in 2002 by majority of companies, was that early application was permitted for entities with fiscal years beginning after March 15, 2001, provided that the first interim financial statements would have not been previously issued (Paragraph 48, Financial Accounting Standards Board, 2001a). Finally, it is important to recall that regardless the date of adoption, goodwill and certain intangible assets with an indefinite life acquired after 30 June 2001 would not be amortised, but

tested for impairment. This means that in some cases SFAS 142 could have to be implemented in mid-fiscal year. An interesting application example is provided in SFAS 142 (Paragraph 50, Financial Accounting Standards Board, 2001b):

“an entity with a December 31, 2001 fiscal year-end would be required to initially apply the provisions of this Statement on January 1, 2002; if that entity completed a business combination on October 15, 2001, that gave rise to goodwill, it would not amortize the goodwill acquired in that business combination even though it would continue to amortize until January 1, 2002, goodwill that arose from any business combination completed before July 1, 2001. Intangible assets other than goodwill acquired in a business combination or other transaction for which the date of acquisition is after June 30, 2001, shall be amortized or not amortized in accordance with paragraphs 11–14 and 16 of this Statement.”

In terms of disclosure under SFAS 142 provisions, most companies reported impacts on results for the two fiscal years preceding SFAS 142 adoption. It is important to note that companies did not measure the impact on results as a result of SFAS 142 adoption. For the fiscal year of adoption, companies reported the *virtual* impact on previously reported results instead, by the means of adjusted results. The majority of the companies adopted SFAS 142 in fiscal year 2002, and reported accordingly impacts for fiscal years 2000 and 2001.

A reduced number of companies did not report SFAS 142 effects for 2000 and 2001, but disclosed impacts only for the following fiscal years of 2001 and 2002. This was the case of Wal-Mart Stores Inc. Wal-Mart's fiscal year-end is 31 January.⁹ According to the Form 10-K filed by Wal-Mart for the fiscal year ended in 31 January 2002 (2002: 23):

“We will apply the new rules on accounting for goodwill and other intangible assets beginning in the first quarter of fiscal

⁸ It is important to note that when a fiscal year does not coincide with the calendar year, then the calendar year in which the fiscal year ends is used in the shorthand. For example, if a company's fiscal year begins in 1 February 2001, and therefore ends in 31 January 2002, it would be then considered as 2002's fiscal year. This is the case of Wal-Mart Stores Inc., as shown below.

⁹ The fiscal years information was collected from EDGAR Online Pro database during the period 2004-2005, and do not correspond necessarily to the fiscal years exhibited in the annual reports that were examined in this research. For example, the fiscal year for NVIDIA corp. ended in 25 January. This closing date corresponds to the year 2004. However, the fiscal years in the period of analysis were slightly different, as ending dates were 26, 27, and 28 January, for 2003, 2002, and 2001, respectively. These rolling dates are the consequence of the adoption of a fiscal year that ends always on the same day of the week. In this case, some fiscal years will have 52 weeks, while a few others will have 53. Using Cisco Systems to illustrate the adoption of this particular type of fiscal year, the company announced that commencing with fiscal year 1997, the company's fiscal year would be the 52- or 53-week period ending on the last July's Saturday (Cisco Systems, 1998). The fiscal 1997 was a 52-week fiscal year which ended in 26 July 1997. The fiscal 1998 was also a 52-week fiscal year, and therefore ended in 25 July 1998. The fiscal 1999 was however a 53-week fiscal year, in order to match with an ending in the last Saturday of July which, in 1999, corresponded to 31 July.

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2003. Application of the nonamortization provisions of the Statement is expected to result in an increase in net income of approximately \$250 million for fiscal 2002. Prior to the completion of the second quarter of fiscal 2003, we will complete a transitional impairment review for goodwill and indefinite lived intangible assets as of the date of adoption. Subsequently, we will perform similar impairment reviews on an annual basis. Management does not believe that the adoption of the impairment review provisions of the statement will have a material effect on the earnings and financial position of the Company.”

It is interesting to observe that not only Wal-Mart supposedly delayed any effective decision on impairment charges under SFAS 142 to 2003's fiscal year, avoiding the so-called “big bath earnings management” occurred in 2002, as it has also reported the impact on results for the first time only in 2002. This was due to the fact that, despite some companies were due to adopt SFAS 142 immediately in 2002, other companies were required to adopt SFAS 142 only in 2003. Indeed, when Wal-Mart filed the Form 10-K for the year ended in January 2002, the new business combinations accounting rules were already enforced, but SFAS 142 adoption was not yet effective, as only for the fiscal year ended in January 2003 was Wal-Mart required to report SFAS 142 effects.

Apart from companies that had to adopt SFAS 142 in fiscal years 2002 and 2003, there was also the case of companies that could be entitled to adopt the new accounting standard earlier. The earliest adoption possible of SFAS 142 was for companies with a fiscal year beginning in 15 March 2001, i.e., ending in 14 March 2002. However, as stated in SFAS 142 (Paragraph 48, Financial Accounting Standards Board, 2001b):

“In all cases, the provisions of this Statement shall be initially applied at the beginning of a fiscal year. Retroactive application is not permitted.”

Apart some exceptions, not applicable in this case, this provision means that Wal-Mart could only adopt SFAS 142 in its fiscal year beginning in 1 February 2002. It cannot be then argued that Wal-Mart deferred SFAS 142 adoption. As Wal-Mart could only adopt SFAS 142 in fiscal year 2003, it has therefore disclosed information on impacts for the fiscal years ending in 2001 and 2002.

For a better understanding of this reasoning, detailed

information on SFAS 142 timings of adoption and disclosure follows. Companies with fiscal years beginning between 15 March 2001 and 14 December 2001 could adopt SFAS 142 earlier, provided that the first interim financial statements would have not been previously issued. Since SFAS 142 was to be adopted unrestrictedly only from the fiscal year beginning in 15 December 2001, early adoption can be considered as optional.

In terms of year of adoption, all companies had to adopt SFAS 142 in fiscal years 2002 or 2003. Companies with fiscal years ending from 14 March 2002 to 31 December 2002, could have adopted SFAS 142 for 2002's fiscal year. Most of these companies disclosed impacts on precedent reported results for the two preceding fiscal years, i.e., 2000 and 2001. However, some disclosed impacts only for the preceding fiscal year of 2001.

Companies with fiscal years beginning from 2 January 2002 to 14 December 2002, had to adopt SFAS 142, as any deferral would constitute a violation to SFAS 142 implementation provisions. It can be then concluded that all companies had to adopt SFAS 142 at least during fiscal year 2003, in case they did not adopted it earlier. Most of companies that adopted SFAS 142 in fiscal year 2003 have disclosed impacts on reported results for the two preceding fiscal years, i.e., 2001 and 2002. However, some companies disclosed impacts only for the preceding fiscal year of 2002.

Finally, all companies with fiscal years ending after 13 December 2003 were due to adopted already SFAS 142, as its latest adoption was required for all companies with fiscal years beginning after 14 December 2002. If a company would adopt SFAS 142 from the fiscal year ending in 14 December 2003 onwards, it would be then violating SFAS 142's adoption provisions.

In resume, companies with fiscal years beginning between 2 January 2002 and 14 March 2002 could only adopt SFAS 142 in fiscal year 2003, while companies with fiscal years starting between 15 December 2001 and 1 January 2002 had to adopt SFAS 142 in fiscal year 2002. Companies with fiscal years beginning between 15 March 2001 and 14 December 2001, and between 15 March 2002 and 14 December 2002, could have adopted SFAS 142 in 2002 or 2003, respectively.

It is therefore possible to make the following generalization: during the period of adoption of SFAS 142, companies with

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fiscal years beginning between 2 January and 14 March had to adopt SFAS 142 in fiscal year 2003, while companies with fiscal years starting between 15 December and 1 January had to adopt SFAS 142 in fiscal year 2002. Companies with fiscal years beginning between 15 March and 14 December could adopt SFAS 142 in 2002, provided that the first interim financial statements would have not been previously issued, or a fiscal year later, in 2003. In case the company had to adopt SFAS 142 during mid-fiscal year, as required by paragraph 50 of SFAS 142, this generalization does not apply.

3.3.3. Impact measurement

Companies reporting under SFAS 142 have disclosed diverse information about the impacts from the nonamortisation of acquired goodwill and indefinite-lived intangible assets. They have also included supplemental statements of income with information about SFAS 142 impacts on both reported and adjusted bases. The measurement of SFAS 142 impacts on previously reported results, included information about the amount of acquired goodwill and indefinite-lived intangible assets not any longer subject to amortisation, and pro-forma figures for net income (or net losses), had the new accounting standard been in effect for previous fiscal years.

One of the most important figures that companies had to disclose under SFAS 142 was the impact on EPS. As a major indicator of a company's profitability, the EPS assumes particular importance in the USA where it is highly regarded. In fact, despite the immense variety of indicators used in financial analysis, EPS is still considered a leading indicator for evaluating share prices.

The FASB requires companies' financial statements to report EPS for each of the major categories of the income statement: continuing operations, discontinued operations, extraordinary items, and net income (Financial Accounting Standards Board, 1997). In order to ensure the homogeneity of the sample, only comprehensive net income figures were used.

SFAS 128, *Earnings per Share*, specifies the computation, presentation, and disclosure requirements for EPS in the USA. Under SFAS 128, two forms of EPS are required to be reported: basic and diluted. This requirement was also followed in SFAS 142, as shown in its Appendix C (paragraph C5, Financial Accounting Standards Board, 2001b).

Basic EPS is computed by dividing income available to

common stockholders, in the numerator, by the weighted-average number of common shares outstanding, in the denominator (paragraph 8, Financial Accounting Standards Board, 1997).

The diluted EPS expands on basic EPS by including the effect of all dilutive potential outstanding common shares. Basic and diluted EPS are therefore similarly computed. However, in diluted EPS computation, the denominator is increased in order to include the number of additional common shares that would have been outstanding if the dilutive potential common shares had been issued (paragraph 11, Financial Accounting Standards Board, 1997).

Diluted EPS is a more consistent indicator than basic EPS. Additionally, while some companies did not report SFAS 142 impact on basic EPS, they all however reported the effect on diluted EPS. Therefore, diluted EPS has been taken in this research as a proxy for measuring the impact of SFAS 142 on reported earnings.

3.3.4. Resume of data collection procedure

As SEC filings were the main data source, a note on its timing follows. In terms of 10-K and 10-K405 forms, considering they need to be filed up to 3 months after the fiscal year has ended, companies with fiscal years ending from 14 March 2002 to 30 September 2002 were due to have their filings prepared in 2002. As for companies with fiscal years ending between 31 October 2002 and 30 September 2003, the 10-K forms had to be filed until the end of 2003. Finally, companies with fiscal years ending after 31 October 2003 were due to file the 10-K forms only in 2004.

In order to ensure that all companies reporting SFAS 142 effects could be identified, the SEC filings from 2001 to 2004 were examined. Although companies did not adopt SFAS 142 in fiscal year 2001, the filings were examined in order to analyse earlier disclosures related to the new business combinations standards. This examination also intended to capture any possible particular or abnormal disclosure. The 2004 filings were also examined, not only to collect information about companies that had to adopt SFAS 142 until the fiscal year ending in 13 December 2003, which had to file the Form 10-K until in the first quarter of 2004; but also to ensure that companies potentially delayed in reporting on new business combinations accounting could still be included in the sample.

This additional data verification has revealed to be important

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as some early disclosures on SFAS 142 would be later revised by a few reporting companies. Whereas the reported information of a more recent Form 10-K, or annual report, conflicted with similar information reported in previous years, the newest information has been the one selected for the final sample. Therefore, for most companies, the search for SFAS 142 effects started with the examination of 2004's filings, even knowing in advance that almost all companies reported such effects in 2002 and 2003 filings.

Finally, the period of 2001-2004 was fertile in financial reporting restatements. Accordingly, some companies filed later amendments, using the Form 10-K/A. In some cases, a half dozen of amendments were filed by a single company during the period 2001-2004. It cannot be assured that every amendment filed has been verified. Additionally, despite similarities in financial reporting, some companies reported

SFAS 142 effects in slightly different ways, forcing in a few occasions to rely on personal judgement in order to harmonize the information made available in annual reports by all companies.¹⁰

3.4. SFAS 142 impacts sample

As discussed before, the sample for analysis is the result of the congregation of data collected from financial reports of companies that completed M&A deals in recent years, and that have reported business combinations accounting changes following the adoption of the new FASB's standards. The annual filings from 2001 to 2004 of the 500 companies that composed the S&P 500 index in 2004 were examined, as this index is considered to be an excellent proxy for the corporate environment where a significant part of the M&A activity is placed. The use of S&P 500 index also ensures a good coverage for the most significant industries in the USA.

Fig. 1 S&P 500 index companies by industry as of 31 December 2004

As shown in Fig. 1, the corporate sectors included in S&P 500 index are quite diversified, being most industries well-weighted. By the end of 2004, financials and the IT industry represented about one-third of S&P 500 companies. Together with consumer discretionary companies, IT and financials accounted for half of the companies in the index.

Following the examination of the 500 S&P's companies, it was been found that more than half of the companies disclosed impacts in the scope of the adoption of SFAS 142. More precisely, at least 257 companies measured and

disclosed impacts on results as if SFAS 142 would have been previously adopted. In addition, another 219 companies referred adoption of SFAS 142, but did not provide any measurement and details of the impact. Some other 4 companies referred the effectiveness of SFAS 142, but did not clarify whether they were entitled for adoption. In resume, only 24 companies did not assume clearly SFAS 142 adoption.

The majority of the companies disclosed impacts for 2000 and 2001, regardless different fiscal years' endings. However,

¹⁰ Any inaccuracy from the data collecting process that may be reflected in the annual reports sample is exclusive responsibility of the author.

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as referred before, a company with a fiscal year ending between 14 March and 13 December could have adopted SFAS 142 only in 2003. In case of adoption in fiscal year 2003, it was then natural to report impacts for 2001 and 2002.¹⁰ As a result of this myriad of possibilities, the sample comprised 257 companies with the following reporting status:

- i. 222 companies disclosed information for both fiscal years 2000 and 2001;
- ii. 10 companies disclosed information only for fiscal year 2001;
- iii. 24 companies disclosed information for both 2001 and 2002; and
- iv. 1 company disclosed information only for fiscal year 2002.¹¹

It was already justified why companies reported SFAS 142 effects in different years. Regardless the year of reporting, what matters for the present research is the homogenised impact on the two fiscal years preceding SFAS 142 adoption. As the large majority of the companies examined, 222 in 257, reported income figures for 2000 and 2001 together with adjusted pro-forma information as if the accounting change

had been already in effect, these two fiscal years were taken as a reference for the final sample.

This assumption means that data in the final sample referred to 2001 is a proxy for the impacts on the fiscal year preceding SFAS 142 adoption, regardless the effective year of adoption by the companies. Similarly, sample data for 2000 is a proxy for the impacts on the second fiscal year preceding SFAS 142 adoption.

In order to homogenise the reporting periods in the sample, the data from the company presenting information only to 2002 (iv) was considered as being referred to 2001; while data for the 24 companies that reported impacts for fiscal years 2001 and 2002 (iii), has been considered as for years 2000 and 2001, respectively. As a result of this standardization, it is implicit that all companies adopted SFAS 142 in fiscal year 2002, despite this not being true for 25 of the 257 companies included in the final sample.

The final sample is therefore composed by 257 companies, contributing with 503 observations, 246 for 2000, and 257 for 2001. The weight by industry for the 257 companies included in the sample is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure -2

Fig. 2 Annual report sample companies by industry

¹¹ However, a few companies disclosing adoption of SFAS 142 in 2003 reported impacts for 2000 and 2001.

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Interestingly, the majority of companies impacted by SFAS 142 were from IT industry, with 18.8% of the total sample. Financials ranked third, and together with IT and consumer discretionary they sum for around half of the companies in the sample.

3.5. Basic descriptive statistics and analysis

In terms of global figures for the sample companies, in 2000, the 246 companies reported an average net income of 897.4 millions in dollars value. In average, had SFAS 142 been made effective in 2000, the same companies would report 968.9 millions of net income, a 7.9% increase. In terms of total values for 2000, the 246 companies reported \$220.7 thousand millions of net income and would report an adjusted \$238.3 thousand millions had SFAS 142 been adopted, as net amortisation of purchased goodwill totalling \$17.1 thousand millions, and amortisation of other purchased intangible assets than goodwill of \$474 millions, would be discontinued, and consequently added back to reported income. Had SFAS 142 been adopted in fiscal year 2000 and the net income of the 246 companies would be therefore increased in \$17.5 thousand millions.

In a similar analysis for 2001, the 257 companies reported an average net income of \$406.6 millions, a 54.6% decrease when compared to 2000. As discussed earlier in this paper, the economic climate changed in the beginning of the 2000's, so this sharp decrease in results can be considered as normal. Had SFAS 142 been made effective in 2001, and the 257 companies would report \$542.3 millions of net income in average, a 33.3% increase. In terms of global figures for 2001, the 257 companies reported \$103.7 thousand millions of net income, and disclosed a pro-forma net income of \$138.3 thousand millions, as net acquired goodwill

amortisation of \$32.9 thousand millions, and amortisation of \$1.65 thousand millions related to other purchased intangible assets than goodwill, such as indefinite-lived tradenames, or workforce intangible, would be added back. Therefore, had SFAS 142 been adopted in fiscal year 2001, and the net income of the 257 companies would be increased by one-third. In face of a period of sharply falling earnings, the immediate adoption in 2001 of SFAS 142 would be certainly welcomed by companies which were amortising purchased goodwill and other intangible assets. If no impairment losses would be recorded, the adoption of SFAS 142, by the means of nonamortisation of purchased goodwill and other intangible assets, would represent a *bonus* of \$34.6 thousand millions in earnings for the 257 companies examined.

3.6. Impact on diluted EPS

Since companies had to disclose the *virtual* impact on EPS for the immediate fiscal years before SFAS 142 adoption, and being EPS a powerful and harmonized indicator, an in-depth analysis focused on diluted EPS follows.

As disclosed pro-forma by 246 companies in 2000, the adjusted diluted net income per share was in average 20.7% superior to the diluted net income as reported.¹² Had SFAS 142 been adopted in fiscal year 2001, and the reported net income of the 257 companies examined would increase 29.6% in average.

Some companies reported a zero impact on reported EPS. More precisely, 7 companies in 2000, and 3 in 2001. Had these companies being excluded from the sample, and the average impact of SFAS 142 adoption on diluted EPS would be of 21.3% and 30%, for 2000 and 2001, respectively. The average impacts on diluted EPS are very much meaningful by all means.

¹² A small group of retailers, including Kohl's Corporation, The May Department Stores Company, and The Kroger Co., adopted SFAS 142 on the fiscal year starting in 3 February 2002. According to them, this adoption was made in fiscal year 2002, and therefore the impacts from SFAS 142 were disclosed for 2000 and 2001. According to the theoretical framework presented in this research, a 2003 fiscal year-end reporting corresponds to fiscal year 2003, not 2002. This framework matches with the views of the remaining companies in the sample. Therefore, had these retailers following the standard views on fiscal year definition, and they would have disclosed impacts for years 2001 and 2002, as if they had adopted SFAS 142 in fiscal year 2003. As this issue is irrelevant for the constitution of the final sample used in this research, it was decided to keep these companies in the group of companies reporting impacts for 2000 and 2001.

¹³ The growth ratio for diluted EPS is expressed as a percentage, and shows the relative growth of diluted EPS over the last reporting period. In some cases, the ratio had to be computed using negative values. In order to allow proper computations of growth using negative EPS values, the following formula with absolute values in the denominator has been employed:

$$\frac{\text{current year's EPS} - \text{previous year's EPS}}{|\text{previous year's EPS}|} \times 100$$

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The diluted EPS sample median was 7.18% for 2000, and 9.52% for 2001. The high discrepancy of the median versus average, 7.18% vs. 20.7%, and 9.52% vs. 29.6%, suggests the existence of outliers biasing the sample average. The impact of companies reporting zero impact is not significant, as revealed by the minor differences between the average percentages for the whole sample versus sample excluded from zero values. Therefore, outliers are not minimum, but maximum values.

Indeed, a substantial number of companies disclosed impressive impacts on diluted EPS, had SFAS 142 been adopted. The maximum impact on diluted EPS reported in 2000 was 4.85 times, or 385%. A total of 10 companies disclosed adjusted diluted EPS with increases of 100% or more. For 5 companies the impact on reported diluted EPS was at least 200%. The sample standard deviation was 0.47.

The impact of SFAS 142 on 2001's earnings would be even more expressive. The maximum impact disclosed was 7.6(6) times the reported diluted EPS, an increase of 666%. 12 companies reported impacts of 100% or more, 6 reported

increases of at least 200%, and similarly, 4 reported 400%, and 3, 500% or more. Unsurprisingly, the dispersion of values was higher than in 2000, and therefore the standard deviation was also higher, 0.77.

A final indication about the significant weight of the outliers follows. For 2000, 48 companies reported differences between adjusted diluted EPS and reported diluted EPS superior to the average of the 246 observations: 20.7%. In 2001, the impact for 51 companies was superior to the average impact for the 257 sampled companies: 29.6%.

4. Cross-sectional analysis

Since the analysis from the survey suggested the existence of significant effects of the new business combinations accounting standards on IT industry, and as the sample for annual reports comprises the same 10 main sectors of activity as for the questionnaires' sample, allowing direct data triangulation, it is therefore of interest to develop a cross-sectional analysis. The cross-sectional data for analysis is shown in Table 1.

Table 1 exhibits the weighted average of purchased goodwill

Table 1 SFAS 142 impacts on diluted EPS by industry

	Weighted avg. goodwill and other intang. assets added back (\$ millions) [†]		Average impact on diluted EPS in percentage (pct.)		Weighted avg. impact in pct. [‡]
	2000	2001	2000	2001	
Consumer Discretionary	42.4	192.7	24.27	30.01	27.18
Consumer Staples	69.7	84.5	10.18	8.82	9.50
Energy	24.6	28.0	11.97	19.43	15.71
Financials	65.4	87.2	18.63	16.30	17.41
Health Care	31.3	39.5	30.22	17.20	23.48
Industrials	94.4	96.5	28.09	34.85	31.53
Information Technology (IT)	87.3	201.6	17.80	66.64	42.48
Materials	40.9	54.3	31.94	19.88	25.74
Telecommunication Services	110.0	134.7	10.43	18.20	14.32
Utilities	23.6	48.1	6.29	12.27	9.29

[†] Weighted average from purchased goodwill, and other intangible assets than goodwill averages. The number of observations used for computing the goodwill added back average corresponds to the number of observations used for computing the impact on diluted EPS average. The number of observations used for computing the other intangible assets than goodwill average is not shown.

[‡] Weighted average for 2000 and 2001's average impacts on diluted EPS.

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and other intangible assets that would be added back for 2000 and 2001, had SFAS 142 being adopted. It is possible to observe that companies from industries such as energy, \$26.3 millions, health care, \$35.4 millions, and utilities, \$35.9 millions, have the lowest average amounts of goodwill and other intangible assets, while, conversely, IT, \$144.4 millions, telecommunication services, \$122.4 millions, and consumer discretionary, \$117.5 millions, exhibit the highest amounts, which are significantly expressive for 2001. In fact, the amounts of goodwill and other intangible assets rose for every industry from 2000 to 2001, but this increase was particularly significant for the companies from the 3 industries with the highest amounts of purchased intangible assets that could be added back under SFAS 142.

In terms of diluted EPS in 2000, utilities recorded the lowest impact, 6.29%. Companies from consumer staples, telecommunication services, and energy, with impacts of a little above 10%, were also in the group of the less possibly impacted by SFAS 142. On the opposite side, materials, 31.94%, health care, 30.22%, and industrials 28.09%, topped the ranking of the industries with the highest impacts.

Overall, impacts on diluted EPS were higher for 2001. Only consumer staples, 8.82%, and utilities, 12.27%, did not exceed by far impacts around 10%. The companies from these 2 sectors were also the ones with the lowest impacts for 2000-2001: 9.5%, and 9.29%, respectively. The highest impacts in 2001 were recorded for IT, 66.64%, industrials, 34.85%, and consumer discretionary, 30.01%. The companies from these 3 industries have also recorded the highest average impacts on diluted EPS for 2000-2001, with 42.48%, 31.53%, and 27.18%, respectively.

Considering that the impacts from 2000 and 2001 can be extrapolated for 2002 onwards, seems justifiable to argue that companies from IT, consumer discretionary, and industrials, were the most affected by SFAS 142 adoption. The overall evidence also indicates that IT companies were the most impacted by SFAS 142. Indeed, not only they had the highest average values of purchased goodwill and other intangibles subject to nonamortisation in 2001, as they were also the ones suffering the most significant impacts on diluted EPS.

5. Caveats

Evidence shown in this paper was not subject to formal statistical testing and validation, and therefore conclusions need to be drawn carefully. An example of the possible consequences of lack of control for statistical assumptions follows. The company with the highest impact on diluted EPS in the sample is from the IT industry, 666% in 2001. Despite the sizeable number of IT companies in the sample, 48 in 2001, had this outlier been removed and the average diluted EPS in 2001 would have decrease from 66.64% to 53.88%. Similarly, the average value of purchased goodwill and other intangibles would decrease from \$201.6 millions to \$201.4 millions. An insignificant impact in this case, however. Overall, the elimination of this outlier, or unusual observation, does not change fundamentally any of the analyses drawn before. However, since it reduces significantly the impact on diluted EPS, it therefore smoothes the prevalence of IT over the remaining industries in what concerns to SFAS 142 effects.

Other major outliers, i.e. impacts over 200% on diluted EPS in 2000 and 2001, are included in health care, financials, industrials, and IT industries.¹³ Although these industries are among the ones with higher number of observations, the corresponding figures and findings need however to be regarded with due care, particularly for single yearly analyses.

Weighted average figures including both 2000 and 2001 are more robust, as the potential effect from possible outliers is more diluted, providing therefore more reliable analyses. Taking again IT industry as an example, had the same outlier been removed and, for the period 2000-2001, the weighted average diluted EPS would be reduced from 42.48% to 35.61%, while the weighted average value for goodwill and intangibles added back would have an imperceptible decrease from 144.42 millions to 144.38 millions.

Nevertheless, although not shown, some sensitivity analysis were performed to ensure that the findings presented in this paper were not significantly biased, and also to minimize the lack of statistical testing and validation.

¹⁴ Outliers' threshold set arbitrarily.

6. Discussion of results and suggestions for further research

From the analysis of 10-K forms and annual reports it was possible to find that the changes in business combinations accounting resulted in significant impacts in the financial reporting. Had SFAS 142 been made effective in 2000 and diluted EPS from S&P 500 companies would have increased 20.7% in average. Similarly, adoption of SFAS 142 in fiscal year 2001 would produce an even more significant average increase of 29.6% in diluted EPS. These positive effects are sizeable enough to do not be neglectful of. Moreover, such impacts are materialised in billions of dollars in purchased goodwill and other intangible assets not to be amortised that, if not subject to significant impairment losses, mean meaningful earnings increases simply as a result of a technical adjustment, i.e., a change in GAAP.

To the best of the knowledge of the author of this paper, this finding is unique in existing literature. However, some authors anticipated or estimated similar impacts under different, but related circumstances. For example, Ayers et al. (2000), using a sample of pooling companies, estimated that EPS would have been considerably lower if purchased method had been used. By the time Ayers et al.' study was made, purchased goodwill and other intangible assets were still amortised over a maximum period of 40 years. This is the reason why the earnings that would decrease in case pooling method would be eliminated.

The Ayers et al. paper is also interesting because, despite a natural *opposite* finding, it brings a *comparable* measurement. In Ayers et al. study, assuming a 10-year amortisation period, the decrease in EPS would be from 8.3% in financial services, up to 42% in food, textile, and chemicals industries. Assuming a 40-year amortisation period, EPS would be reduced from 2.2% to 15.7%, in financial services and in the hotel and other services industries, respectively.

As FASB dropped the initial proposal on replacing a 20-year amortisation period for impairment tests, it has reversed entirely the impact on earnings, in a scenario of absence of impairment losses. Comparing the initial FASB's proposal with the final provisions of SFAS 142, from possible losses over 15% in some industries, to average increases in earnings of more than 20%.

Another interesting outcome from the evidence shown in this paper relates with the big bath earnings management occurred in 2002. It seems arguable that the replacement of amortisation of acquired goodwill and other intangible assets with definite life by impairment tests may have eased the recognition of impairment losses immediately upon initial adoption of SFAS 142. Indeed, the positive impact from nonamortisation of goodwill and other intangible assets has diluted, in some cases significantly, the negative impact on corporate earnings of impairing companies. A finding that certainly deserves further examination together with new evidence that continues to emerge from research on SFAS 142 effects.

The evidence collected from the annual reports of S&P 500 companies also corroborates the findings of literature pre-pooling of interests elimination, signalling a possible impact of the accounting changes on M&A activity in IT industry. This strand of literature expressed public concerns from the IT sector about the proposed elimination of pooling of interests (see e.g. King, 2000; King & Kelly, 2000; *Prepared Testimony of Mr. Dennis Powell Vice President and Corporate Controller Cisco Systems*, 2000). Indeed, from the cross-sectional analysis shown in this paper, it is suggested that IT industry may have suffered some impacts from the changes in the accounting regulation. Whether such effects were enough to impact M&A activity on IT industry is not definitive and therefore offers an additional opportunity for further research. ■

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